

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Genetic studies of flag leaf angle in indica and japonica rice crosses

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Flag leaf angle is an important trait in a rice ideotype. We studied the genetic behavior of flag leaf angle in five indica/japonica crosses 1987-90.

The parents and the F_1 and F_2 of five crosses were grown in a randomized block design with three replications; the F_3 was grown with one replication. Seedlings were transplanted at 16.5- × 26.0-cm spacing, one seedling/hill. The angle between the flag leaf base and the stalk was measured at full heading.

Flag leaf angle tended to be similar to the shorter parent in the F_1 (Table 1). The frequency distribution in the F_2 was continuous, suggesting that flag leaf angle is controlled by multiple genes. Broad-sense heritability was 66.7-82.5%, and genetic advance based on 5% selection differential for flag leaf angle was 29.8-57.3% in the F_2 . Narrow-sense

Table 1. Genetics of flag leaf angle in different generations of indica × japonica crosses. Chongqing, China, 1990.

Cross ^a	Parents		F ₁		F ₂			F ₃		
	P ₁	P ₂	\bar{X}	H ^b	\bar{X}	h ² _B ^c	GA ^d	GA ^e	\bar{X}	h ² /N
Yumidao/C Pei 211, japonica/ indica	45.7	9.5	26.2	-0.08	21.3	82.5	-12.2	-57.3	23.9	70.9
C Pei 211/Yigen 3, indica/japonica	9.5	52.6	22.7	-0.39	18.4	77.8	-9.5	-51.7	20.4	65.5
Milyang 23/Yigen 3, indica/ japonica	12.0	52.6	28.5	-0.19	32.4	66.7	-13.8	-42.6	30.1	61.4
02428/Erluizezao, japonica/indica	12.4	21.8	15.2	-0.40	14.6	75.2	-5.5	-37.7	15.8	68.2
Erluizezao/02428, indica/japonica	21.8	12.4	16.5	-0.13	17.1	73.4	-5.1	-29.8	16.3	61.9

^aC Pei 211 and 02428 are wide compatibility lines. ^bDominance. ^cBroad-sense heritability. ^dGenetic advance. ^e% of mean (negative GA indicates tendency to small angle). ^fNarrow-sense heritability.

Table 2. Correlations^a between flag leaf angle and other traits in F₃, Chongqing, China, 1990.

Crosses	Flag leaf			Plant height	1000-grain weight	Single-plant yield	S ^b	T ^c
	Length	Width	Area					
Yumidao/C Pei 211	0.12	0.20	0.20	0.10	-0.23	-0.31*	0.52**	0.67**
C Pei 211/Yieen 3	0.26	0.21	0.22	0.16	-0.26	-0.37**	0.48**	0.56**
Milyang 23/Yigen 3	0.24	0.21	0.14	0.20	-0.19	-0.31*	0.66**	0.70**
02428/Erluizezao	0.18	0.20	0.19	0.17	-0.24	-0.28*	0.82**	0.60*
Erluizezao/02428	0.17	0.19	0.15	0.19	-0.24	-0.30*	0.71**	0.61*

^aSignificant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. ^bSecond leaf angle. ^cThird leaf angle.

heritability, calculated by the F_2 - F_3 regression, was 61.4-70.9%.

In the F_3 , flag leaf angle did not correlate with flag leaf length, width, area, plant height, or 1000-grain weight. It was, however, correlated positively and significantly with second and third leaf

angle, and negatively and significantly with single plant yield (Table 2).

This heritability and genetic advance of flag leaf angle imply that direct selection for flag leaf angle in early generations is effective. □

Genetic variability in root and shoot characters of selected rice genotypes

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We evaluated the genetic variability and heritability of nine traits in 22 rice genotypes grown in an aeroponic culture system for 45 d in the IRRI phytotron glasshouse.

All traits showed wide variation (see table). The phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV) were higher than the genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV).

Range, mean, coefficients of variability, and heritability of 9 traits in 22 rice genotypes grown under aeroponic culture. IRRI, 1987.

Character	Range	Grand mean	SE	PCV	GCV	ECV	Heritability (%)
Radicle length (cm)	2.53 - 4.75	3.32	0.29	22.68	16.67	15.36	54.05
Radicle thickness (mm)	0.43 - 0.60	0.49	0.01	8.90	7.64	4.56	73.08
Root length (cm)	25.81 - 45.35	35.21	2.11	18.0	14.69	10.40	66.62
Root thickness (mm)	0.50 - 0.87	0.73	0.04	16.21	12.85	9.88	62.86
Root dry weight (g)	0.17 - 0.50	0.35	0.05	31.30	18.95	24.91	36.67
Shoot dry weight (g)	0.57 - 1.36	1.00	0.12	29.27	20.52	20.74	49.12
Root-to-shoot ratio	0.21 - 0.42	0.36	0.02	14.96	10.39	10.76	48.28
Tiller number	1.67 - 4.00	2.40	0.42	40.71	27.71	30.40	44.43
Plant height (cm)	46.02 - 90.01	74.11	2.95	13.55	11.66	6.80	74.06

Radicle length, root length, root dry weight, shoot dry weight, root-to-shoot ratio, and tiller number showed comparatively higher environmental coefficients of variability (ECV). This indicates that these traits were more sensitive to environmental and agroecotypic factors.

Comparatively high heritability for root length, root thickness, and plant height indicates that these characters are governed by additive gene effects; and high recovery for these traits can be expected in early generation selection. □